

Dr. Ambedkar views on Dalit Women Empowerment to the Contemporary Andhra Pradesh Society

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Abstract—Dr. Ambedkar is popularly famous as the drafting committee chairman of the Indian constitution, and also famous as an icon of a Dalit rights movements in the country. Ambedkar involved as the freedom fighter, political leader and revivalist of Buddhist in India. He believed women have a key role to play in emancipation of oppressed communities. His main effort was to liberate Dalit Women from social, religious ties and to access them deprived of education, inheritance. As chairman of drafting committee introduced statutes for the betterment of Dalit women lives based on social justice. He felt that irrespective of the caste, creed, gender and religion everybody should be treated equal. He worked for the liberation of women and their rights. Till the Ambedkar's existence made efforts for the society to follow path of Liberty, Equality and Fraternity. Ambedkar faced ill treatment, humiliations and caste-based barriers right from his school days, still exists in the society. In his lifetime Ambedkar faced evils of society from the roots of society and offered suggestions and remedies to remove them.

This paper focuses on Dr. B. R. Ambedkar perception on Dalit Women Empowerment in Andhra Pradesh. The paper includes the contribution of Dr. Ambedkar's thoughts and ideas towards Dalit women empowerment. This paper also given to highlight the relevance of Ambedkar at present day circumstances.

Keywords: Ambedkar, Dalit, Hindu Marriage, women rights

I. DALIT WOMEN IN INDIA

Ambedkar perspective on women role to play in the emancipation of oppressed Dalit women, and believes this can be achieved by ensuring Dalits women rights to property, education. He was supporter of emancipation of women.

Ambedkar inspired Dalit women for the cultivation of the mind and spirit of self help. According to him the progress of a Dalit women is measured by way of progress which Dalit women achieved. He wanted to see Dalit women not their slave. Ambedkar believed that education important to play for women. He supported Dalit women by giving them rights and role in political and social field. While bringing changes in favor of women under the HMA,1955 (Hindu Marriage Act, 1955).

Lack of Women Education in Scheduled Caste and Schedule Tribe Dalit women localities. Across India different social and economic reasons are influencing the Dalit women's education. Reasons for the higher rate of illiteracy among the Dalits:

- Resistance from the family and fear of insecurity in villages
- Lack of facilities like accommodation, school transport, and medical facilities
- the Dalit girls are forced to take care of their brothers, sisters when the parents are at work
- working & earn for the family, which took the girl away from girl school
- working with parents and earn their livelihood in beedi and cigar factories made them illiterate
- sick and unemployment of parents, Dalit girls stop schooling and marriage at younger age

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar role in Dalit women's education includes opening schools and accommodation and as barrister helped Dalit Women with legal aid. Few important points

- Dalit women are the largest socially segregated groups in the world, and 20 per cent of their population.

- Dalit women discriminated because they are poor, women and are Dalits.
- Dalit women discriminated by the higher caste people, and in their own community.
- Dalit women life is worst in India. They are sufferers of social, cultural, political, economically. Dalit women effected with oppression and violence.
- Dalit women worry are bound less. They are suffering by all kinds of social and economic oppression.

II. AMBEDKAR VIEWS ON WOMEN RIGHTS AND SOCIAL JUSTICE

Ambedkar believes women have the right on their own body and conception was a choice that women have to make. Ambedkar mentioned for reproductive rights for women, and recommended for birth control facility made available to them, and he fought for women's reproductive freedom. His aim was to make a society based on social justice. This implies all benefits and privileges in the society to be available to all its members. His work on Dalit women's rights is overlooked, and he is to be recognized as a champion of social justice, philosopher, visionary and. on gender inequality in Indian society he raised his voice to include Dalit women in modern society. He believes Dalit women's participation in both personal and professional angles. Ambedkar involved in drafting legislation to protect women's rights and involved in reducing working hours and working conditions. Ambedkar's moral values relevance to social justice and his goal for a society based on social justice. To achieve women empowerment, In the provisions of constitution he including number of provisions. According to Ambedkar him, sexual discrimination has to be rooted out from the society. Men and women should get equal opportunity without Discrimination.

Ambedkar through agency provides freedom of choice to women, which led to Dalit women empowerment. His contributions of women empowerment is the Hindu Code Bill, led to equality without discrimination. His social justice is on liberty, dignity and which Indian constitution guarantees equal rights irrespective of caste.

III. AMBEDKAR ON EMPOWERMENT OF DALIT WOMEN

Dalit Women Empowerment led to health and social development of families, communities. When Dalit women are living in productive lives, Dalit women can reach to their full potential. Dr. Ambedkar is a determined fighter and a good scholar lead the society based on Liberty, Equality, Fraternity in Preamble of Constitution. He is the first Indian to remove barriers in the way of advancement of Dalit women. He mentioned women be given all round development and social education, for their wellbeing and social cultural rights. He mentioned each and every section of Dalit women can give their share to maintain and protect dignity of women. His contribution to the women's empowerment includes Maternity Benefit Act, 1961 provision in Constitution. In which pregnant ladies gets paid leaves till the delivery. He played role in the formation of the Hindu Marriage Act, 1955 and worked on the inclusion the right to divorce, adopt, and marry.

Ambedkar fought for women's rights; and also continuously worked for Non-Discrimination. He worked in reducing the number of working hours for Dalit Women and to improve working conditions. In Legislative Council Ambedkar included granting Maternity Benefit for Dalit women working in factories. His opinion that if employer getting benefits of women labour, employer should be supporting women, when Dalit women are on maternity leave. He supported the movements led by Dalit women. Women must deny the life of slaves. Ambedkar worked on journals Mook Nayak 1920, Bahiskrit Bharat 1927. He made strong movement against the Hindu social order.

IV. LEGISLATIONS FOR DALIT UPLIFTMENT BY AMBEDKAR

As the father of Constitution Ambedkar included civil liberties such as freedom of religion, removal of untouchability, removal of discrimination. In Constitution he written fundamental rights it includes the upliftment of Dalits.

V. FUNDAMENTAL RIGHTS AND DPSP'S OF DALIT LABOUR INCLUDES

Article 13(2) "The continent shall not make any act which takes away or abridges the rights by this part and any act made in this contravention be void".

Article 14 "State not deny to any citizen's equality before the law and equal protection of laws".

Article 15 "Fundamental rights of Citizens against discrimination on the basis of religion, race, caste, sex, place of birth".

Article 15(4) "Legislations for socially, educationally backward classes of Dalit Women".

Article 16(4A) "State can make any provision with consequent seniority in the services under the State in favor of Dalits".

Article 16(4B) "Unfilled vacancies filled accordance with provision for reservation".

Article 17 "Untouchability is an offence punishable under law". for the protection of Dalits under Legislations such as Civil Right Protection Act 1965, Prevention of Atrocities Act 1989

VI. VARIOUS DPSP'S OF DALIT WOMEN INCLUDES

Article 243 "Panchayat's must have reservation of Dalit Women".

Article 330 "Reservation of seats in the Lok Sabha, Rajya Sabha for Dalits"

Article 332 "Reservation of seats for Dalits in Legislative Assemblies"

VII. ANDHRA PRADESH NATIONAL RURAL EMPLOYMENT GUARANTEE SCHEME (APNREGS)

Govt. introduced National Rural Employment Guarantee Act 2005. This Act gives legal guarantee of hundred days in a financial year to Dalit women labor, this act applicable in Districts mentioned by the Government of India.

The objective is to enhance the financial security of Dalit Women. This addresses drought, deforestation, soil erosion etc. Which improves the employment generated to the lives of Dalit Women Labor.

VIII. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Ministry of rural development introduced various rural development programs for Dalit women Includes MGNREGS, IAY, DWACRA, SGSY, JGSY, IRDP, JRY etc.

Govt. of Andhra Pradesh programs to upliftment of rural Dalit Women includes DEEPAM, INDIRAMMA etc. All the programs available directly or indirectly the rural Dalit women.

Rural development programs on Dalit women is unexplored area in India and There is necessity for investigation of rural development programs

Though after six decades rural development programs. Not effected the Dalit women

IX. CONCLUSION

The Constitution includes equal rights to all Indian citizens, right to live with equality, honor and dignity. Still the caste and untouchability are playing negatively in different parts of the society. According to Ambedkar Nation is facing social, economic, educational, political evils in the society and effective implementation of Constitution can overcome them.

The Dalit Women have to work hard in all social, economic, educational, political fields. Elite caste has to be more generous towards Dalits regarding untouchability and upliftment of social economic, educational and political status etc. In social structure of our society Dalit women are the people who perform all types of menial works to be avoided by elite class.

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